

D1.6 Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication and Outreach (DECO) Final Strategy

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List of acronyms

- Agricultural Knowledge and Information Systems (AKIS)
- Committee of Regions (CoR)
- Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)
- Communication (Comms)
- Communication coordinator (Comms coord.)
- Community of Practice (CoP)
- Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication and Outreach (DECO)
- European Commission (EC)
- European Network of Rural Development (ENRD)
- European Union (EU)
- Multi-actor Platform (MaP)
- Non-Governmental Organisation (NGO)
- Value Chain (VC)
- Virtual Research Environment (VRE)

1. Introduction

The **overall objective** of the MOVING project is to build capacities and co-develop - through a bottom-up and participatory process that involve value chain actors, stakeholders and policy-makers – the relevant policy frameworks across Europe for the establishment of new or upgraded/upscaled mountain Value Chains (VCs). The mountain value chains are key to contribute to the resilience and sustainability of mountain areas.

Over the course of the project, the following specific objectives have been identified and pursued to address the above-mentioned overall objective:

1. **To engage the main actors and stakeholders** into a European-wide Community of Practice (CoP) on Mountain VCs.
2. **To develop a conceptual and analytical framework** able to describe and interpret the diversity of mountain VCs and assess their contribution to the sustainability and resilience of mountain areas and population.
3. **To provide easy-to-read visual tools** that raise the awareness of AKIS, VC actors, civil society and policymakers on the diversity of land use and production systems of mountain areas, the threats they face, the bio-physical assets they can mobilise, their sustainability, and their resilience to Climate Change.
4. **To study the configurations, the strategies, the dynamics and the value distribution of the VCs** in the main European mountainous areas (EU member states and associated countries) in order to assess their contribution to sustainability and resilience.
5. **To develop participatory and critical benchmarking of clusters of mountain VCs** to identify enablers and blocking factors affecting sustainability and resilience.
6. **To carry out evidence-based foresight exercises** (at community, cross-regional and European levels) to capture and anticipate the long-term trends affecting mountain areas.
7. **To develop a policy roadmap** and a ‘Quick Start’ policy design based on evidence-based and performance focussed recommendations to secure a long-term provision for the ‘next generation’ of policy interventions.

The Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication and Outreach Strategy (hereafter DECO or the ‘Strategy’) has been instrumental in achieving these objectives, supporting all project activities, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Links between project Work Packages

The MOVING Strategy is conceived as a dynamic, living document that is designed to adapt and evolve through regular updates. This approach ensures the strategy remains relevant and responsive to new information, emerging opportunities and evolving trends. The strategy is developed to enhance coordination and create synergies between the activities of MOVING, and the work of relevant stakeholders in the field.

To reflect the project's accomplishments, the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) on communication defined in the Grant Agreement and the [D1.1. DECO Strategy](#) were updated in [D1.4 DECO Activity Report \(year 1-2\)](#), submitted in August 2022 (M24). The Table below reports the updated target for the end of the project (M48).

Table 1. Updated Key Performance Indicators

Key Communication Output	KPI	Initial Target (M48)	Updated target (M48)
Website	Number of downloads of documents from the MOVING website	2 000	2 500
	Number of unique visitors	5 000	7 000
Social media	No of LinkedIn followers	200	350
	No of Facebook followers	200	220
	No of Instagram followers	Launched in August 2021	220
	No of Social Media impressions	25 000	300 000

As we present this final version of the strategy, it encapsulates the cumulative insights and lessons learned from ongoing monitoring and evaluation processes. This ensures that the final recommendations and actions proposed are well-informed and aligned with the project's overarching goals.

The following sections detail the key features of the final version of the Strategy, including:

- Objectives of the Strategy
- Target audiences
- Narrative
- Activities
- Communication channels
- Deliverables
- Timeplan
- Exploitation
- Monitoring, evaluation and update.
- Lessons learned and recommendations

In **January 2024**, a survey was launched among MOVING partners to evaluate, adjust and update the communication and dissemination strategy. Survey's results are integrated in the document.

2. Objectives of the strategy

The Strategy adopts a **four-step approach** that has matured alongside the project. To begin with, the Strategy created a cohesive and distinct identity for the project to enable the **discovery** of MOVING by the target audiences, and foster familiarity with its goals and activities. This set the stage for the subsequent phase, which concentrated on fostering **engagement** with key stakeholders.

With the project in its concluding phase, the Strategy pivots towards a more intensive **dissemination** of the outcomes and results achieved, ensuring they are communicated effectively to a broad audience. The goal is to address the enhancement of the project's **legacy**, by disseminating findings and ensuring that these results are utilised and integrated into relevant fields and practices. By doing so, the Strategy aims to secure lasting impact, especially by facilitating the uptake of its outcomes and results within and beyond the project's scope.

Table 2. Specific objectives of the Strategy

Specific objective	Description
SO.1	To raise awareness of project aims and activities (DISCOVERY)
SO.2	To facilitate and promote engagement of partners, relevant actors and target audiences in the MAPs (ENGAGEMENT)
SO.3	To inform about project outcomes and results and enable multipliers and the media to share relevant information (DISSEMINATION)
SO.4	To facilitate the uptake of project outcomes and results within and beyond the scope of the project (LEGACY)

3. Guiding principles

The Strategy was formulated to raise awareness among stakeholders about the role of VCs in mountainous regions in fostering resilience and sustainability, and to empower them with the necessary tools and knowledge for future value chain creation. In essence, the Strategy moved beyond simple awareness, serving as a **catalyst for action and empowerment**.

Key to this transformative approach is the active engagement of all target stakeholders. The Strategy requires stakeholders to not just passively receive information but to actively participate in evolving towards improved policy design and implementation for mountain VCs. This transition requires a strong commitment from the audience, which implies giving them compelling evidence, knowledge and tools.

To facilitate this enhanced engagement and stimulate interaction among target audiences, the initial and final Strategy adhere to the following guiding principles:

- **Specificity.** While communications in H2020 projects can sometimes seem abstract, our activities present facts and information that are digestible and practical for target audiences to implement.
- **Resonance.** Target audiences must feel/see the direct and indirect benefits that they derive from outcomes of the project. In order to improve action, the project shows how the results affect them personally, economically and environmentally, as well as socially and globally.
- **Connectivity.** Using carefully tailored methods and tools, including social media and the Virtual Research Environment (VRE) to boost engagement and encourage interaction and dialogue, target audiences share what they are doing while discovering what others are developing, which act as an inspiration and a driver for mutual learning and knowledge exchange.
- **Results-based approach.** Focused activities to achieve specific, measurable outcomes.
- **Continuous learning.** Diligent research, analysis, execution, and assessment that continuously feeds and improves planning and action. This includes constantly getting stakeholder feedback to improve the Strategy, and also flexibility to adjust scope and approach to relevant developments over time.

These principles underscored the Strategy's progression from fostering project discovery to ensuring that MOVING's legacy of enhanced policy frameworks for mountain value chains endures beyond the project's lifetime.

4. The DECO task force

A Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication and Outreach (DECO) task force was established at the beginning of the project to ensure that all partners are involved in the design and implementation of the DECO strategy. This team, comprising at least one representative from each partner organisation and coordinated by AEIDL, focused on enhancing communication and dissemination efforts across the MOVING project. The roles and responsibilities of the DECO Task Force are:

- To ensure the relay of information upwards/downwards;
- To report the different communication activities carried out by their organisation, as well as their impact (Monitoring Tables);
- To identify and adapt the communication messages to each region;
- To identify the main communication objectives per region/country;
- To translate the main dissemination/communication material.

Figure 2. Structure of the DECO task force

Throughout the project, this task force convened for several online meetings. For instance, ad-hoc session was organised to introduce the MOVING communication channels, including the website, social media channels and the newsletter. Communication guidelines and the communication monitoring tool were equally presented. Follow-up meetings were organised to deepen the understanding of the project's communication and dissemination channels, products, and activities. It also explored potential synergies and multiplier effects. A specific focus was placed on the project's Community of Practice, discussing its potential to significantly contribute to achieving the project's objectives.

In this final phase of the project, specific sessions and exchanges will be organised to support partners in the dissemination of MOVING's results. To this end, in **January 2024**, AEIDL mapped partners' demands in terms of training and specific support for the upcoming months. It particularly emerged the need to foster partners' ability to produce briefs and synthesised content, engage with policy and decision-makers to disseminate the project's

results, and writing news and press releases. These areas will be prioritised by the Communication and Dissemination Lead (AEIDL).

Figure 3. Areas for guidance and training

5. Target audiences

5.1. Geographical coverage

Regarding the geographical coverage, the Strategy is implemented across EU Member States (MS) and partner countries involved in the project. When implementing the Strategy, MOVING considers national differences and local stakeholders, striving to ensure a balanced and inclusive approach. At a secondary level, MOVING has made efforts to engage with other non-EU MS that are relevant to the project, thus extending its reach and impact beyond the European Union.

5.2. Stakeholder mapping and analysis

The Figure below presents a revised version of stakeholders targeted by the final CODE Strategy, ranked in order of relevance. Stakeholders have been identified to align with the specific project's objectives described in Section 2, which now focus on the **dissemination** and **legacy** of the project. In addition, based on the survey conducted in January 2024, partners ranked target audiences in order of priority (Figure 4 below) for disseminating MOVING's results.

Figure 4. MOVING target audience in order of priority

- **National/Regional policy-makers:** Policy and programme designers, political decision-makers at national and regional levels, and municipalities.
- **European-level policy-makers:** European level organisations/institutions (e.g. European Commission, European Parliament, EU Committee of the Regions, RUMRA & Smart Villages Intergroup).
- **Policy implementers:** Local administrations; managing authorities; LEADER Local Action Groups; Community-Led Local Development (CLLD); local planning initiatives (e.g., Local Agenda 21, rural mayors' networks).
- **Mountain communities/organisations:** grassroot players and civil society organisations within mountain areas.
- **Rural and mountain networks at global, European, national level:** Euromontana, FAO Mountain Partnership, EU CAP Network, National Rural Networks, FARNET, European Rural Parliament network, ELARD, Natura2000 stakeholder networks, ECOLISE.
- **Industry and businesses within the mountains VCs:** Representative bodies of farmers, landowners, forest managers, processors, rural businesses, and actors in the food chain, with a focus on consumers.
- **Grassroot players** (e.g., actual or potential beneficiaries and participants in EAFRD and relevant Horizon projects, Operational Groups, EIP-Agri groups, farmers and land managers, advisers, consultants).
- **Scientific Community:** Universities, Research, Institutes, Scientists (external and internal to MOVING consortium).
- **Civil society,** particularly from mountain communities across Europe (e.g., through European Rural Parliament events and national rural parliament events), or rural and

urban communities and with a special focus on youth, environmentalists, NGOs, consumers, and disadvantaged groups.

The Strategy establishes different levels of engagement for these stakeholders, classifying them within an alignment/influence – interest matrix (Figure below). This matrix includes three dimensions:

- **Alignment:** The extent to which the stakeholders align with MOVING’s goals and approach.
- **Interest:** The extent to which the stakeholders are already engaged in the issues or the field of MOVING (e.g., are they committing resources, speaking out, setting objectives).
- **Influence:** The degree to which the stakeholder can sway the debate.

The combination of these dimensions results into three potential options:

- **High alignment / high interest** and **low alignment / low interest** are classic boundary partners.
- **High alignment / low interest** would be characterised by a stakeholder that broadly shares the same objective but does not have the availability to invest time and resources in the project such as a local organisation with a very limited budget.
- **Low alignment / high interest** would be a stakeholder that is funding work in the same area as the project, but with a different objective.

Figure 5. Stakeholder alignment/influence – interest matrix

5.3. Multipliers

This Strategy aims at achieving a maximum impact with controlled spending by selecting channels that are the most effective in reaching out to the various target groups and **building upon multipliers**, namely consortium partners and relevant stakeholders at EU, national, regional and local levels, which can contribute to maximise the potential audience of the MOVING project. Multipliers have been invited to share the core messages, practices and ultimately the results of the project using their own communications channels, and tools.

MOVING is **built on multipliers** as follows:

- Within the project partnership, the multiplier effect is ensured by the involvement of **national and regional organisations** that have a strong and well-structured presence at local level, with a widespread and multi-stakeholder membership. Furthermore, the local focus is reinforced by the international and cross-country approach, giving a new impetus to the debate and offering new instruments to change the narrative, thanks to exchange of information, models, tools and best practice with partners from other countries.
- At the regional level, the multiplier effect is based on **linking with societal actors** through regional workshops.
- At the national level, relevant stakeholders for **policy analysis** are involved in a “policy process” that are based on policy audits at a regional level and one EU level workshop.
- At the European level, the multiplier effect relies first on the involvement of **key research and stakeholder organisations** that are well connected with **EU institutions and networks** (e.g., ENRD, EU CAP Network, AREPO, Euromontana, FAO Mountain Partnership etc.) from inside and outside the consortium.
- **Media**, for the purposes of the Strategy, are not perceived as target audiences, rather as multipliers. Press networks and associations, journalists and news providers in the Brussels bubble and at national level can become fundamental multipliers in delivering our message and informing about MOVING and its outcomes. Two factors are to be decided when compiling the relevant list of press contacts: (i) To which media do our target audiences pay most attention to?; and (ii) Which media will consider our messages newsworthy?. While we will consider all media as potential multipliers, most of the focus will be placed on online media with an interest in the themes addressed by MOVING.

Our goal is to turn identified multipliers into a solid network that promotes our ideas, convey our messages and help us reach our objectives.

MOVING’s communication pathways to impact are enhanced through a co-constructed, multi-actor approach that focuses on the end-users of its findings and recommendations. These involve representatives of organisations which have written in support of MOVING from across end-user and stakeholder communities.

5.4. Targeting per specific objective

The specific target audiences corresponding to each Specific Objective (SO) are identified as illustrated in the following table. **Highlighted in yellow** are the most important objectives for this final phase of the project, and the relevant stakeholder groups.

Table 3. Link between specific objectives and target audiences

Specific objective	Description	Target audience (in alphabetical order)
SO.1	To raise awareness of project aims and activities (DISCOVERY)	Business and industry, CAP and National Rural networks, Environmental NGOs, European-level policy-makers, Horizon projects/networks, Media, Mountain Organisations, National/Regional policy-makers, Policy implementers, Researchers, Rural dwellers, Mountain communities, Value Chain consumers.
SO.2	To engage partners and target audiences in the MAPs promoted by the project (ENGAGEMENT)	Business and industry, CAP and National Rural networks, Environmental NGOs, European-level policy-makers, Horizon projects/networks, Mountain Organisations, National/Regional policy-makers, Policy implementers, Researchers, Rural dwellers, Mountain communities, Value Chain consumers.
SO.3	To inform of project outcomes and results (DISSEMINATION)	Business and industry, CAP and National Rural networks, Environmental NGOs, European-level policy-makers, Horizon projects/networks, Media, Mountain Organisations, National/Regional policy-makers, Policy implementers, Researchers, Rural dwellers, Mountain communities, Value Chain consumers.
SO.4	To facilitate the uptake of project outcomes and results within and beyond the scope of the project (LEGACY)	Rural dwellers, Mountain communities, Environmental NGOs, European-level policy-makers, Mountain Organisations, Researchers, Policy implementers, Business and industry, Value Chain consumers.

6. Narrative

6.1. Marketing techniques

We use specific marketing techniques to effectively communicate our messages, focusing primarily on storytelling and co-design.

- **Storytelling.** This involves using videos, articles, and social media to present authentic examples of value chains in mountain regions or to showcase the project's outcomes. We emphasise best practices and highlight leading actors and organisations that have successfully achieved their goals. A significant aspect of our storytelling approach included integrating materials from the projects in the EC RURAL-01 Call (PoliRural, SHERPA, RURALIZATION). With these projects concluded, we are now shifting our strategy to build synergies with Horizon Europe projects like Mount Resilience and MARGISTAR. Additionally, from now on, this strategy will be employed to build a story based on MOVING results. For example, our analysis of vulnerabilities and subsequent strategies for improvement have led to the development of future scenarios for mountain regions. These scenarios, along with a Repertoire of Strategic Options, will significantly contribute to the development of our Policy Roadmap.
- **Co-design for engagement.** Recognising that effective change cannot be solely driven by a top-down approach, MOVING involves stakeholders, especially in the regional MAPs and the EU MAP, in co-creating communication and dissemination actions. This collaborative approach not only fosters engagement but also facilitates the exchange of ideas, knowledge and arguments. A key element in successful stakeholder engagement is initiating conversations that resonate with the target audience's interests and priorities, subsequently exploring pathways/solutions within the rural development narrative.

6.2. Key messages

MOVING's key messages are tailored for each target audience and are continuously refined and updated over the course of the project. Initially, a set of messages was proposed at the beginning of the project:

- Mountain areas form the ecological skeleton of Europe providing essential environmental, social and economic goods and services.
- Mountain areas are under significant pressure from climate change, depopulation, poor infrastructure, including telecommunications, and the low profitability of some of their economic activities.
- New value chains and opportunities are emerging in mountain areas.
- A new generation of policies is needed to address a fair environmental, socio-economic and digital transition, with the involvement of the different actors, that guarantees the future of mountain areas.

- Mountains are vulnerable to climate change, yet climate change mitigation (e.g. reduce emissions from livestock; reforestation) may challenge traditional livelihoods and cultural landscapes.

Over the course of the past three years, initial messages have evolved or been refined based on project progress and results. Additionally, following the survey conducted in January 2024, partners have shared their insights regarding the initial key messages, proposing new ones or modifications to existing ones.

As a result, the **key messages for this final Strategy** are as follows:

- **Mountain areas, the ecological skeleton of Europe, need effective collaboration between mountain stakeholders and civil society** to maintain existing value chains and cultivate new ones, fostering a fair and sustainable transition while safeguarding their rich culture and heritage.
- **Mountain areas are under significant pressure** from climate change impacts, depopulation, inadequate infrastructure, low economic profitability, and conflicts of use among various activities such as sports, agriculture, and mass tourism.
- **Mountain regions can turn climate challenges into opportunities by adopting an integrated approach** that harmonises grassroots and policy-driven strategies, innovation, and adaptive measures. The key to success lies in robust multi-level governance and decentralized institutions.
- **The new generation of policies should not only ensure a fair environmental, socio-economic and digital transition but also strive to reverse historical marginalisation**, unlocking the potential of mountain value chains to secure a thriving future for these regions.
- **Mountain communities are the driving force behind the protection and development of mountain regions.** Their active involvement and advocacy are essential for safeguarding these vital areas and fostering sustainable progress.
- **Mountain areas are forging innovative paths towards shared solutions**, fostering collaborative communities, and developing socio-ecological systems that offer fresh insights into climate change management and its consequences.
- **Embedding the desires and needs of youth into EU policies for mountain regeneration and prosperity is key** for the effectiveness of these policies.

7. Key communication outputs

The Table below presents the upcoming MOVING's outputs until the project's end and their communication pathways.

Table 4. Key MOVING communication outputs

MOVING outputs (upcoming)	Main Target Audience	Communication Product ¹	Communication channels
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¹ Responsibilities for the delivery of the outputs are defined in the Grant agreement.

<p>D1.9: Practice Abstracts (2nd batch) (Month 48)</p>	<p>Regional, national or European-level policy-makers Mountain organisations and communities Value chain stakeholders Advisors Researchers</p>	<p>Individual Practice Abstracts Short Article/Blog</p>	<p>CoP Social Media Newsletter Website</p>
<p>D2.3: Final Conceptual framework (Month 46)</p>	<p>Researchers Regional policy-makers Advisors Horizon projects/networks Mountain organisations and communities</p>	<p>Report Short Article/Blog Interview</p>	<p>CoP Social Media Newsletter Website</p>
<p>D2.4: Final set of Policy Briefs (Month 46)</p>	<p>Regional, national or European-level policy-makers Mountain organisations and communities Value chain stakeholders Advisors Researchers</p>	<p>Individual Policy Briefs Short Article/Blog</p>	<p>Website Newsletter Social Media CoP</p>
<p>D6.3: Synthesis report, including a Repertoire of Strategic Options (Month 40)</p>	<p>Regional, national or European-level policy-makers Advisors Researchers Mountain organisations and communities Environmental NGOs Business and industry Value Chain consumers. Horizon projects/networks</p>	<p>Report #4 Podcast Short Article/Blog Infographic</p>	<p>CoP Social Media Newsletter Website</p>
<p>D7.1: Policy Roadmap including recommendations for a new generation of public policies and</p>	<p>Regional, national or European-level policy-makers Mountain organisations and communities</p>	<p>Report #5 Podcast #3 Video Short Article/Blog</p>	<p>CoP Newsletter Social Media Website</p>

strategies for Europe's mountain areas (Month 46)	Horizon projects/networks Environmental NGOs CAP and National Rural networks Business and industry Value Chain consumers Advisors	Infographic	
D7.2: Policy Audit and Policy Design Toolkit (Month 48)	Regional, national or European-level policy-makers Mountain organisations and communities Horizon projects/networks CAP and National Rural networks	Report Policy Audit Policy tools Short Article/Blog	Website CoP Newsletter Social Media
D8.13: Clustering and synergies with other EU projects (Month 48)	Horizon projects/networks Mountain organisations and communities	Report Short Article/Blog	Website Social Media

8. Communication activities

8.1. Building on existing communication tools and initiatives

Communication activities are established and developed with partners' channels and networks (e.g. –AREPO, UCO, AEIDL), existing relevant structures (e.g. Euromontana, FAO Mountain Partnership) and others. Also, collaborations include the use of well-established European-level channels such as the Rural Pact Support Office and the EU CAP network, with which project partners have a good track record of engagement and participation.

Last but not least, cooperation of the European Commission is sought for establishing cross-posting, to make use of the capacities of EU institutions and EU networks (e.g., EC, EESC, Committee of Regions, CAP Network, Rural Pact) and links to EU CORDIS news and Cordis Results in Brief, CORDIScovery podcasts, the Horizon Magazine, and the Research & innovation success stories.

8.2. Visual Identity

One of the fundamental pillars for a wide and efficient dissemination of the project's results of is a coherent and consistent visual identity. For this reason, MOVING developed a visual identity package, which consists of:

- Visual style guide (Book of Style), including all the guidelines for perpetuating the MOVING brand identity in all external and internal communications.
- Visual identity in several formats.
- Social media banners.
- Template for the newsletter, which was updated in M22 to make it more attractive and engaging.
- Template for Deliverables, which was updated in M34. It now includes a "Status" field indicating whether a deliverable is "submitted" (to the European Commission) or "approved" (by the European Commission).
- Template for PowerPoint presentations.
- Templates for News items.
- Templates for Policy Briefs and Practice Abstracts.
- Visuals for multimedia material (e.g., videos).
- Relevant promotional material to be used in dissemination activities:
 - Roll-ups
 - Leaflet, which have been translated into 12 languages
 - Poster templates
 - Other materials based on needs

8.3. Website

The MOVING website (www.moving-h2020.eu), coded using WordPress, is the primary hub of information for the project, providing a 'one-stop shop' for resources, news, and key information on relevant initiatives. It is linked from the rest of communication and dissemination materials produced under the framework of the project.

A first version of the website was launched in November 2020, with a significant update occurring in February 2021. Regular improvements have been implemented since then, incorporating new sections and content. The main sections of the website are dedicated to:

- **Information** about all members of the consortium as well as information of every work package.
- A **library** including all documents, Deliverables, infographics, Practice Abstracts, Policy Briefs, articles, reports, etc.
- A **dedicated space for the Reference Regions/MAPs**, which offers in-depth information about each MAP's context, goals, activities, and expected outcomes/impacts, etc. These pages are updated accordingly with the latest documents, news articles, and developed videos pertaining to each region.
- The **EU MAP webpage** has also been updated with the EU MAP activities.
- Reporting on **news and events** carried out within the framework of the project, highlighting MOVING events and other relevant events for our target audience. In

addition to the news section, the official newsletter is also considered to be in this section on the main menu.

- Our **Tools section** introduces Story Maps, inviting users to explore interactive maps on an external site, which highlight the unique attributes and challenges of our 23 selected Reference Regions, as well as the 453 value chains identified by MOVING across Europe.
- A repository for the **Digital Stories** with 23 concise videos, providing a comprehensive overview of the vulnerability of mountain value chains in both European and neighbouring countries.
- An archive of **Practice Abstracts**, showcasing all the Practice Abstracts developed by the project, each categorized by Reference Region and encompassing our project findings.
- The **MOVING Podcast** “Conversations on sustainable mountains” is directly linked to the Spotify profile.
- The **visual tools** database presents vulnerability levels, threats and assets of all Reference Regions, making complex data more comprehensible through visual representation.
- The **MOVING Mountain App** subsection promotes the availability of this project outcome, offering guidelines for its installation on mobile phones.

Our website analytics are GDPR compliant, ensuring user privacy while we track engagement. The website complies with best practice in design for ensuring user accessibility (e.g., colour, font, text formatting) to respect the capabilities of readers and contributors (complying with EC Information Providers Guides; <http://ec.europa.eu/ipg>).

Upon the completion of the MOVING project, we will transition our website into a comprehensive archive, showcasing the project's significant achievements and findings. This digital legacy will serve as a testament to our collaborative efforts and a resource for future initiatives in sustainable mountain development. The MOVING's website will be kept alive beyond the project's lifetime, as set in the Grant Agreement.

8.4. Practice abstracts

The resulting innovative knowledge and easily accessible end-user material from MOVING feed into the EU CAP network's website. The end-user material to be produced contains a substantial number of summaries for practitioners in the EIP common format ("practice abstracts"), including the characteristics of the project (e.g., contact details of partners, etc).

A practice abstract is a short summary of approximately 1 000 to 1 500 characters (word count-no spaces) which describes the main information/recommendation/practice that can serve the end-users in their daily practice. Guidance and templates for these practice abstracts are available on the following web address: <http://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/content/eip-agri-common-format>.

A total of 121 practice abstracts are produced, containing all the outcomes/recommendations which are ready for practice. 31 (D1.8) were delivered in Month 24; 58 (D1.9) will be produced by Month 48. There are also 31 practice abstracts (D4.7) from

the regions with the most practical insights (Month 32) and one on Participatory Theory Building (D2.3) in Month 12.

To enhance accessibility and visual appeal, a uniform template for MOVING Practice Abstracts has been designed. Furthermore, a dedicated subsection named "[Practice Abstracts](#)" has been established on the project's website. Initially it was located under the 'Library' section, but after the review meeting, we have relocated to the 'Reference Region' section. This area serves as a repository for showcasing all the Practice Abstracts developed by the project. These documents are organised by Reference Region and the general ones with project findings.

8.5. Social media

Dedicated social media accounts were established within the first month and have become essential **interactive tools** for engaging with our target stakeholders. These platforms serve as a hub to carry out a correct communication and dissemination of the project by sharing news, progress and results, as well as interesting data and figures related to MOVING. To cater to diverse audience preferences and needs, we use interactive formats such as videos, to efficiently convey information to stakeholders with limited time and a preference for easily digestible content.

Based on our experience on the target audience's preferences, we have identified [Twitter](#) and [LinkedIn](#) as our **primary social media channels**, while [Facebook](#), [Instagram](#) and [YouTube](#) are considered secondary platforms.

In addition, the communication team has explored the feasibility of employing additional and newer Social Media platforms for the benefit of the project, such as TikTok. However, given internal functionalities and a shortage of proprietary images and videos, the decision was made not to adopt TikTok as a communication channel.

Visual elements play a crucial role in enhancing our messages across social media channels. Appealing visuals are employed to capture the attention of the followers/audience and invite them to read and learn more about the topics we present. Moreover, we use illustrative elements like banners to establish a consistent brand identity and visual presence for the project.

To share information and content with other partners, we have created a database, with all the addresses of the partners' social networks. This helps us maintain a coordinated and more effective online presence for the project through the connections and partnerships that are established.

Cooperation of the European Commission is sought for establishing cross-posting, making use of capacities of EU institutions (e.g., EC, EESC, CoR). Furthermore, we aim to establish links with EU CORDIS news, CORDIS WIRE, and the Horizon Magazine websites to amplify our project's reach and impact.

To ensure easy identification by our target audiences across all platforms, we have adopted a unified project 'handle': **@movingH2020**.

8.5.1. Twitter

The MOVING Twitter account (@MOVINGH2020) was established in September 2020, and officially launched during the project's Kick-off Meeting on 14-16 September 2020. This account, managed primarily in English, serves as the project's central corporate social media channel. To cater to a more localised audience, additional accounts have been set up. For example, the coordinator, UCO, has managed the account @H2020Moving_UCO serving the audience in Spanish language and covering the three Reference Regions in Spain. The Communication Manager (AEIDL) manages the official Twitter account, with contributions from the project partners.

This channel is used for short news flashes, employing a clear and concise style, not too descriptive or institutional. It serves as a platform for instant communication and engagement with the target audiences from society, science and policy. We use dedicated hashtags to streamline communication related to specific project products and actions, e.g., #MOVING2020, #MOVINGforesight, #MOVINGworkshop, #MOVINGDeliverable, #MOVINGconference, etc. These hashtags facilitate connections and discussions beyond physical meetings.

Twitter also plays an important role during projects events, where live tweeting enhances knowledge sharing and community-building. This practice fosters connections among participants, panel experts, remote audiences following the events.

Our team commits to enhancing the project's visibility by:

- Posting relevant news and updates related to the work done by the partners under the MOVING project at least once a week;
- Following relevant accounts from stakeholders and engaging with them (e.g., retweet);
- Creating conversation with followers, sparking debate on hot topics addressed by MOVING, and gathering their views;
- Providing relevant content by third parties (information on latest trends and new relevant developments);
- Post or retweet about events, reports and initiatives from other projects or other activities from relevant stakeholders;
- Promoting events and strategies that are integral to the MOVING project's objectives.

8.5.2. LinkedIn

LinkedIn facilitates networking with people and professional organisations, particularly those from the private sector and academia within our target audience. Our company page, (MOVING - Mountain Valorisation through Interconnectedness and Green Growth) was launched in September 2020 to serve as a central hub for staying informed about MOVING developments and sharing information with relevant stakeholders.

Similar to our approach on Twitter, we employ dedicated hashtags to streamline communication related to specific project products and actions, such as #MOVING2020, #MOVINGforesight, #MOVINGworkshop, #MOVINGDeliverable, #MOVINGconference, and more. These hashtags play a crucial role in facilitating connections and discussions beyond

physical meetings. To ensure the effective use of our LinkedIn account, we employ the following strategies:

- Share status update to engage with our network. These updates can include thought-provoking questions related to our project or industry, sharing news, or providing insights that align with our project's goals. This activity will be coordinated with our Twitter timeline to maintain consistency across platforms.
- Actively identify and connect with individuals, companies, researchers, policy-makers, and other professionals who may have an interest in our project's results. Inform about upcoming events and meetings organised under this Strategy. This includes sharing event details, agendas, and highlights to generate interest and encourage participation among our connections.
- Showcase project milestones, achievements, and significant developments.
- Actively monitor and respond to comments and to demonstrate our commitment to fostering meaningful conversations and collaboration.
- Share multimedia content such as videos, infographics, and presentations, as well as insightful articles and research findings to convey our project's key messages and findings.

8.5.3. Facebook

In September 2020, we launched a dedicated Facebook page as a component of our communication strategy. This page aims to reach out to MOVING stakeholders, especially those who may not be fully covered by LinkedIn. It is a channel tailored for public outreach and showcasing our project's outputs, providing a more informal and community-oriented environment for engagement.

To maximize the impact of our Facebook page, we implement the following strategies:

- Maintain an active presence by posting regular updates, news, and highlights related to MOVING. This content is coordinated with our Twitter timeline to ensure consistency across platforms.
- Leverage the power of visuals by sharing images, videos, and infographics that showcase the project's impact and activities.
- Participate in Facebook groups related to mountain and rural areas to connect with a broader audience and foster meaningful discussions.
- Promote project events, including workshops, webinars, and meetings.

As we do on Twitter and LinkedIn, we employ dedicated hashtags to streamline communication related to specific project products and actions. These hashtags, such as #MOVING2020, #MOVINGforesight, #MOVINGworkshop, #MOVINGDeliverable, #MOVINGconference, and others, facilitate connections and discussions.

8.5.4. YouTube

In March 2021, we launched a dedicated YouTube channel, serving as a central repository for all of the project's multimedia content. This channel is designed to host and provide access to a diverse range of content, both current and forthcoming. The content includes:

- Introductory videos featuring the 23 Mountains RRs and their associated VCs.
- Explanatory videos detailing the MOVING approach and methodology for Participatory multi-level foresight, as well as the Conceptual Analytical Framework.
- Specific sessions from the EU MAP webinars.
- Digital Stories that delve into the vulnerability and resilience of our value chains.
- Interviews with project partners to promote upcoming deliverables.
- Outcomes and highlights from the project.

Our YouTube channel simplifies the sharing of these videos on social media platforms through short links. Additionally, some of our videos, such as those from the EU MAP webinars and the Digital Stories, are embedded on our website via YouTube for easy access and viewing.

8.5.5. Instagram

The MOVING Instagram account was established in August 2021 with a clear objective: to share captivating images from project events and provide insights into our project's activities. Additionally, we use this platform to share European updates that are relevant to our target audience. To harness the full potential of our Instagram presence, we employ the following strategies:

- Share highlights from project events, workshops, webinars, and meetings.
- Use Instagram Stories to provide real-time updates during events, and create engaging, eye-catching posts to recap the key takeaways.
- Repost user-generated content to build a sense of community and engagement.
- Create Story Highlights to categorise and permanently showcase important content, such as project milestones, key findings, and events.

8.6. The Virtual Research Environment

The **Virtual Research Environment** (VRE) is the key digital working platform available for the Consortium and the participants from the CoP and regional MAPs. This dynamic space is serves as a catalyst for intensified interactions among actors and stakeholders, fostering an ongoing exchange.

The VRE supports bidirectional communication, facilitates information sharing, offers storage capabilities, enables social networking, and even encompasses activity tracking mechanisms.

Five VREs have been established to support various aspects of the project:

- **Coordination Management VRE:** Dedicated to the administrative and managerial aspects of the project, ensuring smooth coordination and management.
- **Project VRE:** Designed to support the overarching project activities.
- **Regional MAPs VRE:** It is used exclusively for the communication among the 23 regional MAPs' Coordination teams.
- **EU Multi-Actor Platform VRE:** Open for stakeholders, this VRE is used to exchange, learn and interact around the topic of resilience to climate change of mountain value chains.

- StoryMaps VRE: A platform conceived to build and share Story Maps on mountain ecosystems and value chains from the 23 Reference Regions of the project, as well as detailing the 453 value chains identified by MOVING across Europe.

The platform will continue serve as a pivotal tool for internal communication within the MOVING consortium, as well as for the storage and management of internal documents.

8.7. Short articles and Blog

Two dedicated sections of the website, '[News](#)' and '[Blogs](#)', have been set up to provide access to relevant articles, blog posts and news. These sections have been designed to foster interactive engagement, debates and exchanges amongst stakeholders about specific news, experiences, events, topics of interest for the project or linked to MAPs' activities and topics.

The blog items and articles have been written by rural stakeholders and MOVING partners about a specific topic relevant for the project. The aim is to share knowledge and information (from the project and about relevant issues for the project) and which is interesting to MOVING partners as well as to external stakeholders. The blogs, articles and news are promoted through MOVING social media channels.

In this final phase, the 'News' and 'Blog' sections will particularly emphasis the promotion of the project's final results.

8.8. Newsletter

The MOVING newsletter contains the main updates of the project, activities and progress of the Regional MAPs, as well as relevant news in the field of sustainable mountain value chains. Additionally, it features information and updates regarding other related Horizon projects.

The newsletter is **published two times a year**, typically in June and December. However, as MOVING approaches its final phase concluding in August 2024, special emphasis will be placed on the last two newsletters. These editions, scheduled for April 2024 and August 2024, will feature the main results of the project, with a particular focus on policy recommendations for mountain value chains. This strategic shift aims to ensure that the project's culmination and its significant contributions are effectively communicated to our audience.

The design of the newsletter aligns with MOVING's visual identity and encompasses contributions from partners, researchers and other relevant stakeholders. Managed through the email marketing service Mailchimp, it complies with the GDPR standards regarding the storage and use of personal data of external and internal actors.

In addition to being a key dissemination channel for relevant information, the newsletter is a communication product in itself, which is **distributed through three channels**:

- **MOVING partners and distribution email list:** With the publication of each newsletter, an email is sent to all the partners of MOVING and to the distribution group (this mailing list is composed of those who signed-up to the newsletter via the website).
- **Website:** All newsletters are stored in a repository on the web, which is accessible to all stakeholders.

- **Social Media:** Dedicated posts are published in the relevant social media channels (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook and Instagram).

We aim to achieve more than **350** subscribers to the newsletter by the end of the project. Dedicated promotional activities are featured to promote further subscriptions to this tool, for instance in participation at external events and meetings attended or organised by MOVING.

Moreover, to maximise reach, the newsletter is translated into the languages of all project partner countries. Mailchimp's "Translate" feature facilitates this process, allowing for automated translation, ensuring accessibility and inclusivity for all our stakeholders.

8.9. Press releases

In the initial DECO Strategy (D1.1), we outlined that at least **two press releases** (one at start of the project, one at the end of the project) were foreseen to engage journalists by linking project's activities to relevant media narratives.

However, as the project evolved, we adapted this approach. Press releases were consistently developed by partners, focusing on significant activities and milestones achieved within the Regional MAPs. This shift allowed for a more dynamic and responsive engagement with the national and regional media.

At EU level, WP1 leaders AEIDL prepared three press releases that captured the essence of key MOVING events. These included the [kick-off meeting](#), the [“Unlocking the Power of Mountain Value Chains”](#) workshop and the [European Foresight Workshop](#) “Shaping the Future for Resilient Mountain Areas”.

To effectively disseminate these press releases, AEIDL used its journalist database to reach pertinent press contacts, specialised media and relevant contacts (e.g. Euromontana, FAO Mountain Partnership). Additionally, the Rural Pact Support Office and the EU CAP Network were informed prior to publication, helping amplify the message.

Partners are encouraged to translate and adapt these press releases to their local/regional context and disseminate them through their channels. By doing so, they ensure the message resonated with rural stakeholders in their native language and addressed specific regional interests. This approach is instrumental to maximise the impact and reach of our communication efforts.

8.10. Podcast

As established in the Grant Agreement, a key component part of our communication and dissemination strategy is the MOVING podcast. Titled [“Conversations on Sustainable Mountains”](#), this podcast is designed to summarise and present the research results from the MOVING project over the last three years.

The objectives of the MOVING podcast are the following ones:

- Synthesize and disseminate MOVING outputs across relevant target groups;
- Contribute to raising awareness about the project and its ongoing and forthcoming activities and results;

- Give visibility to MOVING experts from the Consortium and Reference Regions;
- Promote collaborations and synergies with other projects, guest speakers, external members, and EU MAP members.

Spanning from October 2023 to August 2024, this podcast series is planned to include five episodes. Up to M42, the series has successfully launched its initial three episodes, each delving into distinct work packages:

- Change and vulnerability in mountain regions, exploring pathways towards adaptation (WP3).
- Challenges and shared characteristics of mountain regions, as well as recommendations for harnessing the full potential of mountain value chains (WP5).
- The upgrading global strategies to revitalise mountain economies (WP4).

The upcoming two episodes will focus on foresight, and how can be used to explore mountain futures (WP6), and on policy recommendations (WP7) to assess the unique needs of mountain territories.

8.11. Multimedia production

8.11.1. Videos & Digital Stories

23 Digital Stories have been produced to ignite curiosity and communicate the most up-to-date concerns of the MOVING case studies across Europe. These stories aim to provide deep insights into the **vulnerability drivers** faced by the 23 mountain value chains. To foster an inclusive and wide-reaching exchange of knowledge, these narratives are presented in the respective national/regional language, complete **with English subtitles**. Additionally, some partners have translated the script of the Digital Stories, enabling the inclusion of subtitles in other consortium countries' languages.

Moreover, MOVING is set to release **a series of 3 videos**, all produced in English, to showcase the project's significant findings:

1. #1: Vulnerability of Value Chain & mountain areas
2. #2: Value Chains Strategic options
3. #3: Policy Roadmap & recommendations

The narrative will be inclusive and will convey key messages targeted to the specific audience, such as policymakers, value chain stakeholders, advisors, researchers, stakeholder associations and networks at EU, national and regional levels.

All video materials are placed on the [YouTube channel](#) of the project and accessible as well from the project website.

8.11.2. Webinars

We have planned a series of 5 Webinars to **foster an interactive learning environment** in which stakeholders feel involved. As on Month 42, we have organised 3 webinars, each of which involved the MOVING EU MAP and was closely aligned with current EU developments:

- [Mountain Value Chains: heterogeneity and innovation](#)
- [European Quality schemes: the added value for mountain value chains](#)
- [Protected natural sites: A constraint or an opportunity for mountain value chains?](#)

In addition, we have combined the **fourth EU MAP webinar** on the topic of Strategic Options with the in-presence EU Foresight Workshop in Brussels (11th January 2024).

To conclude this series, a **final webinar** on the MOVING's policy recommendations and roadmap is planned in the Spring of 2024, ahead of the Final Project Conference. This approach will allow us to provide a comprehensive and cohesive presentation of strategic options and their implications for policy development.

Webinars are related to knowledge developed in MOVING and support targeted audiences to take **ownership**. Webinars are recorded and placed on YouTube and accessible through the project website. This supports the communication and dissemination through social media channels.

8.12. Final MOVING Conference

An interactive final MOVING conference will be organised at the end of the project, in June 2024, in Brussels, Belgium. The coordination of the conference will be led by AEIDL, the WP Lead on communication and dissemination. The event is designed for a specific target audience of 100 attendees, as defined in the Grant Agreement.

This conference will be tailored around maximising the interaction among participants bringing together the key project results and strategic recommendations and key experts and decision makers, conceiving the Final Conference as a platform to inform the priorities of the EU Institutions for the 2024-2029 Term as well as a springboard for the post 2027 proposals for EU Cohesion Rural Development and CAP for mountain value chains. Tools such as live tweeting and instant surveys or real time visualisation will help to consolidate the MOVING knowledge community, as well as audience following the event through social media and, if possible, live streaming.

All conference materials will be open source, publicly available through the MOVING website. All materials of the events will comply with best practice in ethical requirements and regulations (e.g., GDPR).

For the final conference, the organising team will outreach specialised EU media. A “press pack” will be prepared and send to media outlets, and a press point will be set up to deliver interview to the press.

8.13. Community of Practice (CoP)

The MOVING CoP is understood as a **European-wide Science-Society-Policy interface** to engage stakeholders in addressing the resilience of mountain value chains against climate change and other threats. This collaborative platform invites stakeholders to contribute to the co-creation and validation of all research outputs delivered by MOVING.

As the central forum for bilateral peer exchanges, the CoP facilitates co-learning and the co-creation of knowledge among a diverse range of stakeholders, including both MOVING partners and external contributors, across various territorial levels (regional and European).

The conceptualisation of the MOVING CoP is transferred into practice through the creation of **Multi-Actor Platforms (MAPs)**, that provide the space for interaction, exchange and learning with stakeholders of the community at all territorial levels (regional and European). Hence, MOVING has created, animated and facilitated 24 MAPs across Europe:

- 23 regional MAPs in each of the project's 23 Reference Regions.
- An EU MAP that extends the reach of these discussions to a continental scale.

Figure 6. Community of Practice

Following the integrated transdisciplinary approach of the MOVING project, these MAPs serve as crucial platforms for engaging with relevant stakeholders across all project activities. This structure not only promotes the exchange of knowledge but also fosters peer learning and interaction between stakeholders, from the local Reference Region level up to broader European contexts. By doing so, MOVING ensures that a diverse range of voices and perspectives are considered, enriching the project's research outputs and enhancing their relevance and applicability across different European mountain territories.

The CoP is considered an important feature of the MOVING's DECO strategy, aimed at disseminating knowledge produced by the project, maximising impact through community ownership of results, and ensuring long-lasting use of the results within a community that seeks to continue after the project.

In the project's final phase, the CoP will focus on the following activities:

- Engaging youth in each regional MAP.
- Disseminating project's final results to regional and European-level stakeholders of the CoP and beyond.
- Organising an EU MAP Webinar to discuss MOVING Foresight Results and Strategic Options.

- Hosting an EU MAP Webinar on MOVING's Policy Roadmap for validation and incorporating suggestions.
- Participating in the MOVING Final Conference in Brussels.

8.14. MOVING MOUNTAINS APP

The ['MOVING MOUNTAINS' App](#) has been designed to **foster engagement with mountain region resilience among both local residents and visitors**. This application facilitates the identification and sharing of information, playing a vital role in connecting people with mountains.

The user interface of the MOVING App is thoughtfully designed to optimize user experience. It begins with a welcoming Title Screen that displays the app's name. From there, users can navigate to the About Screen, which offers a comprehensive project description. The Home Screen, having undergone several updates, now effectively consolidates News, Blog, and Events into a single location, mirroring the content found on the MOVING project website. This screen employs a user-friendly "vertical infinite scroll pattern," allowing for smooth and intuitive navigation through dynamic feeds.

The About page integrates all information, including a carousel that details the Project Objectives. The Events page is thoughtfully organised to display upcoming events in a chronological sequence. Additionally, the app provides functionality for mobile and tablet users to bookmark their favourite events and integrate them into their personal calendars for timely reminders. A dedicated action icon on the app ensures streamlined access to types of content, including public, supervised, and mediated content like Project About and News.

In the Community area, users can explore geo-referenced content produced by the Community of Practice. For those with authorized D4Science platform accounts to access MOVING VREs or Gateways, the app provides the capability to upload media, thereby enriching the community feed with images and movie clips. This feature establishes the app as a comprehensive hub for both project information and community-generated content.

Following the release of its final version, the focus will shift towards promoting the app. An article highlighting its usefulness and providing instructions will be published, as well as a [dedicated subsection under the "Tools" section](#) on the MOVING website. It will also be promoted on the MOVING's social media channels to broaden its reach and impact.

Figure 7. Some screenshots of the MOVING Mountains App

9. Dissemination

Dissemination plays a pivotal role in ensuring the broad reach and impactful application of the MOVING project's results. It involves sharing these findings with potential users, such as local stakeholders, researchers, and policy-makers, to maximize the project's value and encourage learning and application of the findings.

To this end, AEIDL (WP1 leader), in collaboration with the project coordinator and the DECO Taskforce, is dedicated to maximizing the dissemination of MOVING's results. This process is monitored through a dedicated tool, ensuring effective reach and engagement. In the Table below is an overview of the dissemination strategy for each key output of the MOVING project.

Table 5. Dissemination of MOVING results

MOVING's Results	Description	Dissemination product	Dissemination channels
D2.2/D2.5 Initial and Final set of Policy briefs	Summarises the key policy recommendations emerged from the project in each MRR	Individual policy briefs	Project website Open Access repositories Policy Forums/Events/ Scientific and non-scientific conferences EU MAP
D2.1/D2.3 Initial and Final Conceptual Analytical framework	Presents the key project concepts and their evolution based on the participatory empirical work	Policy Brief (2 ²) Peer Review publication (1) Practice Abstract (1)	Academic journals Project website Scientific conferences Newsletter EU MAP Open Access repositories
D3.1 Land Use Systems and Land Cover Map in 23 Reference Regions	Describes farming and forestry systems across 23 MOVING RRs and their dynamics		Scientific journals Project website Open access repositories
D3.2 Land use systems and vulnerability matrixes and vulnerability maps for the 23 reference regions	Identifies the vulnerability to key drivers of change of the 23 MOVING land use systems	Peer review publications (1) Practice abstract (1) Visual tools	Project website Scientific publications Presentations at conferences EU MAP Open access repositories
D3.3 Tools for science-society-policy interfaces	The Virtual Research Environments is a platform for data exchange, fostering collaboration. Story Map Building Tool allows to describe value chains and regional concepts	Story maps Scientific publications	Project website Demonstration at conferences Open access repositories Scientific journals

² KPI defined in the Grant Agreement.

D4.1 Inventory of Mountain value chains	Details over 400 value chains in EU mountain areas, including innovation levels and related natural resource systems	Infographic Story maps Peer Review publication (1)	Project website Presentations at conferences Scientific journals Open access repositories Newsletter
D4.2 List of selected value-chains and relationship building	Identifies 23 MRL value chains and their stakeholders for participatory analysis	Story maps Infographic	Project website Newsletter
D4.3 Participatory analysis of value chains	Illustrates how value chains assemble and interact, with implications for sustainability and resilience		Academic publications Project website Presentations at conferences
D4.4 Digital stories from each reference region	Visualises value chains, their regional context and vulnerability assessment.	Digital stories	Project website Public engagement events Newsletter Media
D4.5 Report on Vulnerability and Resilience Performance of 23 Reference Region Value Chains	Identifies vulnerabilities and resilience of 23 MRL value chains, suggesting improvements	Practice abstract (1) #1 Video	Project website Academic journals Presentations at conferences EU MAP
D4.6 Global Upgrading Strategy	Identifies what changes are recommended by the MRL MAPs to improve the performance of the VC	Peer review publications (1) Practice abstract (1) #3 Podcast	Project website Scientific journals Presentations at conferences
D4.7 31 Practice Abstracts	Identifies key issues in native and English for each case study region, guiding practitioners and users	Individual practice abstracts per Reference Region (23)	Project website Newsletter Social Media channels EU CAP network channels
D5.1 Comparative cross-case report on Mountain value chains	Identifies five key clusters of value chains within European MRRs that contribute to sustainability and resilience	Peer review publications (4) #2 Policy Brief #2 Podcast	Academic journals Project website Presentations at conferences Workshop
D5.2 Policy Briefs	Corresponding to the five clusters, these briefs communicate cluster outcomes, raise awareness, and guide evidence-based decisions	Individual policy briefs per cluster (5)	Project website Policy Forums Newsletter EU MAP Presentation at conferences Open access repository
D.6.2 Foresight report per reference region (CONFIDENTIAL)	Presents a report for each reference region.	Infographic Blog article	Project website Presentations at conferences
D6.3 Synthesis report, including a Repertoire of Strategic Options	Consolidates findings and outcomes	Policy Brief (1) #4 Podcast Peer review publications (2) #2 Video	Project website Academic journals Open Access repositories Presentations at conferences EU MAP Webinar (1)

D7.1 Policy Roadmap including the results of the Policy Audit and recommendations for a new generation of public policies and strategies for Europe's mountain areas	Offers an attractive policy perspective with priorities and timeline for mountain areas	Peer review publications (1) #5 Podcast #3 Video	Project website Newsletter Webinar (1) Participation in conferences/policy forums Media EU MAP Webinar Open Access repositories
D7.2 Policy Design Toolkit	Presents 'quick start' tools for adaptive policymaking in mountain areas	Policy Audit Policy tools	Project website EU MAP Newsletter Presentations at conferences Policy Forums Webinar Open Access repositories

This strategic dissemination approach ensures that MOVING's results are effectively communicated to the relevant audiences, fostering knowledge transfer, policy influence, and practical application.

9.1. Online repository (Zenodo)

An online repository was created and managed to store MOVING main results and make them accessible to external users within the limits of Intellectual Property Rights. To this scope, Zenodo online repository was chosen. Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>) is a general-purpose open access repository that allows further dissemination of the project's results in the scope of ensuring their sustainability and long-term impact.

The online repository was created by the project's coordinator, who is managing it in collaboration with AEIDL. As new results become available, they will be promptly added to the MOVING Zenodo community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/moving-h2020-project/>). This approach ensures that the repository remains up-to-date and serves as a valuable resource for interested parties seeking access to the project's research and outcomes.

10. Exploitation

While dissemination activities are important to share the project's tools and results, these activities alone will not guarantee the maximum possible long-term impact of the project's work. Therefore, concrete actions will be taken to ensure that end-users take advantage of and use the results and tools developed to achieve the project's objectives. To this end, an **exploitation plan** has been thoughtfully developed with the advice and support of **the Horizon Booster services**. AEIDL and UCO have led this process, in consultation with WP Leaders and other project partners.

In MOVING, exploitation revolves around getting stakeholders to effectively use the developed tools and results. MOVING results have a strong public nature. The methodologies and tools developed during MOVING will be made fully available to potential users through toolkits. Therefore, it is not foreseen to generate results that will be protected by exclusive licences.

Since an early stage, the **MOVING Key Exploitable Results (KERs)**, and the activities to effectively guarantee their uptake by end-users, have been identified and defined in a set of dedicated workshops on exploitation that involved MOVING WP leaders and MOVING partners, as well as through the Horizon Booster services. Before Month 18, a workshop to identify the preliminary list of Key Exploitable Results and activities (draft exploitation plan) was carried out. By June 2023, a second workshop to identify the MOVING joint and individual exploitation pathways was organised.

An updated version exploitation was finalised before August 2023, and its results were included in the Second Periodic Report (August 2023). Between August 2023 and January 2024, AEIDL and UCO refined the project's exploitation strategy with the support of the Horizon Booster services.

The MOVING exploitation strategy has been consolidated into **three main KERs**, namely:

- 1) The MOVING Conceptual Analytical Framework;
- 2) The MOVING Regional Tools:23 Mountain Areas Vulnerabilities and Opportunities through Value Chains;
- 3) The MOVING Policy Tools.

For each of the above-mentioned KERs, the MOVING Exploitation strategy details:

- A **characterisation** of the given KER (description, unique selling point, alternative solutions, target market, go to market strategies);
- **Use options**: Priority activities to exploit the KER, detailing between direct and indirect uses;
- An **exploitation roadmap**, outlining key steps to enable the effective use of the KER, revenue streams, financial costs, impact in the medium-term;
- A **risk-assessment and priority map**, identifying and evaluating the probability and impacts of risk factors which might hinder the project's exploitation.

The Table below summarises key elements of the MOVING's exploitation strategy in terms of KERs, background elements, use options, target market, impact (3-years' time) and major risks. The extensive version of the project's exploitation strategy, as described in the points above, is available in Annex 1.

Table 6 MOVING Exploitation (Short version)

KERs	Background	Use Options	Target market	Impact in a 3-year time	Major Risk Factors
<i>Conceptual Analytical Framework</i>	D2.4 Conceptual analytical framework (final version)	Direct use: a new research project pursued	Scientific audience (e.g., Universities, research centres)	Deepen the understanding of mountain value chains' interactions and dynamics; Contribute to identify key points for leveraging mountain value chains' enhancement	Weak exploitation: Inadequate business plan; CAF having gaps and inconsistencies; Disagreement on further investments: some partners may leave, Disagreement on ownership rules. Remedial action: Definition of a clear exploitation strategy; through peer review of CAF; complying with Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement's contractual arrangements and duties; Deploying existing technical infrastructure and expertise.
<i>23 Mountain Areas Vulnerabilities and Opportunities through Value Chains</i>	D3.1 Land Use Systems and Land Cover Map in 23 Reference Regions D3.2 Land use systems and vulnerability matrixes and vulnerability maps for the 23 reference regions	Indirect use: spin-off services	Mountain value chains' actors, in particular businesses and practitioners (from different sectors: tourism, agriculture, forestry); Regional Decision Makers Regional and local authorities; Wannabe-entrepreneurs	Increase the capacity of mountain value chains' actors to address current and future threats; Identify, improve and rollout upgrading strategies for mountain value chains; Develop a network of regional mountain stakeholders improved skills	Limited uptake by Mountain Value Chains; Partners break out and create competitive products; Lack of technological structure to collect all tools together. Remedial action: active promotion of tool directly with MVCs; complying with Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement's contractual arrangements and duties;
<i>Policy Tools</i>	D2.5 Final set of Policy briefs D7.1 Policy Roadmap including the results of the Policy Audit and recommendations for a new generation of public policies and strategies for Europe's Mountain areas D7.2 Policy Design Toolkit D6.3 Synthesis report, including a Repertoire of Strategic Options	Indirect use: development of a new legislation/standard	Policy and decision-makers at local, regional, national and European levels	Ensure that MOVING's results are reflected in a number of key European, national and regional policies and strategies; Raise capacity-building initiatives, programmes and projects to enhance mountain resilience and sustainability	Market Demand. Products are not developed in proper timing, Limited uptake from EU decision makers; No resources (human and/or financial) secured to make the next step toward exploitation. Remedial action: policy tools made in sync with evolving EU policy cycle and actively promoted at key decision making stages; Reliance over advocacy groups within MOVING network and other EU stakeholder networks.

11. Timeplan

The timeplan presented below delineates the strategic planning and execution phases for communication and dissemination activities under WP1. Each milestone up to M40 represents a pivotal point in the project lifecycle where specific activities are completed.

From M42 onwards, the focus shifts to consolidating the project's legacy:

- Presenting and implementing the final DECO Strategy, tailoring our communication and dissemination efforts to highlight the project's outcomes and ensure lasting impact as we approach the project's culmination.
- Consolidating the final project's communication and dissemination activities, supporting partners in an effective and successful delivery of this crucial stage.
- Developing the final DECO Activity Report (M48) to evaluate our communication and dissemination efforts throughout the project lifecycle to analyse successes, challenges, and learnings.
- Releasing the final set of Practice Abstracts (D1.9).
- Organising the Final Conference to showcase the project's achievements and key results, emphasising their implications for policy development and future perspectives.

12. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Indicators of success will inform the progress towards achieving project's objectives. The proposed KPIs below are defined in the Grant Agreement and the Strategy (D1.1). Given the substantial advancements we have made to date, we are now setting a more ambitious target for M48. We aim to reach the below targets by the end of the project.

Table 7. Key Performance Indicators

Key Communication Output	KPI	D1.1 Target (M48)	D1.4 Updated target (M24) (M48)	Final Target (M48)
Website	Number of downloads of documents from the MOVING website	2 000	2 500	2 500
	Number of page views on MOVING website	50 000	50 000	50 000
	Number of unique visitors	5 000	7 000	15 000
	Number of visits to the VC map & inventory	1 000	1 000	1 000
Social media	No of Twitter followers	1 000		1 000
	No of LinkedIn followers	200	350	800
	No of Facebook followers	200	220	300
	No of Instagram followers	-	220	300
	No of Social Media impressions	25 000	300 000	400 000
	No of views in YouTube to the videos + webinars	2 000	2 000	3 500
Newsletter	Number of subscribers to the Newsletter	350	350	350
Synergies	No of meetings from H2020 project in which MOVING participated	5	5	12
MOVING App	No of download	200	200	200

13. Lessons learned and recommendations

This section outlines the main lessons learned and recommendations drawn from the combination of five types of data sources:

- Web Analytics (qualitative and quantitative data from the campaign websites, looking at audience, acquisition and user behaviour);
- Social Media Analytics (performance and the effectiveness of the social media channels);
- Online Listening (impact of communication messages in the online public sphere and the extent to which these messages have seeded online conversations). These conversations may be featured in social networks, websites;
- Communication and Dissemination monitoring tool (an online tool to be provided by AEIDL to keep track of all the communication activities developed by the consortium, as well as the impact reached in terms of number of readers / attendees to a conference, etc.).
- The analyses of the online internal survey that was conducted in January 2024 among partners.

13.1. Lessons learned

Lessons learned represent the knowledge gained during the project development. The review of lessons identified **positive aspects to be reinforced**, as well as **challenges and bottlenecks** to be reconsidered. From the analysis carried out, it is understood that MOVING's communication and dissemination activities are on the right track.

The following aspects of communication and dissemination actions have been outlined as **strengths and success factors** of the project so far. These are listed by categories.

DECO Implementation:

- Good alignment of CODE efforts with project objectives.
- Good visual identity, with strong visual appeal, encourages stakeholder to get in touch or follow the project's channels.
- Timely distribution of key news items, articles, and events via VRE to prompt partners for broader communication and dissemination.
- Good frequency in the distribution of project's content, progress and results.
- Really strong and active team, with very good synthesis and continuous looking for opportunities to enhance the Strategy's implementation.
- More than half of MOVING partners share regularly and/or often information about the project's results and updates with local/regional actors. The remaining 45% share them 'sometimes'. Partners share information mainly primarily through workshops and events organised by their respective organisations, organisation's social media accounts and email.
- Appropriate dissemination of results to European-level stakeholders.
- Strong networking connections have been established with other Horizon projects, European organisations, and initiatives.

Channels:

- Effective use of different media platforms to communicate the project progress and disseminate its results.
- The project's website confirms to be the key channel to get informed and learn about the project. In addition to it, VRE is identified as the most useful communication and dissemination channels by MOVING partners for internal communication, followed by the MOVING newsletter for overall project's updates.
- The project website offers extensive, easily comprehensible information and user-friendly navigation.
- A rise in subscribers to both the newsletter and the project's YouTube channel, reflecting the accessibility of project results and the production of diverse video content.

Content & Products:

- Language is concise, clear, and straightforward, enhancing accessibility, comprehension, and strong appeal for targeted audiences.
- The project's newsletter and social media are particularly appreciated for being simple, concise and attractive.
- According to partners, the most useful content to support MOVING's communication and dissemination are (orderly): Publications (research findings, deliverables), webinars and events, and blog posts and project's news on MOVING website.
- MOVING's documents and deliverables are aligned with the project's brand identity, they are visually appealing and enriched with illustrative graphics and figures.
- Around 60% of survey's respondents (January 2023) claim that materials and products are adequately targeted to key audiences.
- In content production, the project shows a well-rounded balance between MOVING-related content and other types of content (e.g. external content, EU-level news).

Nonetheless, throughout this exercise and analysis, ***weaknesses and challenges*** have been identified that will require the implementation of specific actions to improve in the future. These have been sorted into different categories:

CODE Implementation:

- Information overload - difficulty in deciding what information to include for clear and concise dissemination.
- Lack of partner expertise in communicating with non-academic audiences.
- Difficulty in tailoring messages to particular needs and organisations. In particular, challenges in reaching local administrators, universities, and researchers for collaboration.
- Difficulty in explaining the complex nature of the project to all audiences.
- Difficulty to keep MAP stakeholders regularly engaged. Challenging to find a good balance between providing useful updates / results / info about upcoming events and not overloading MAP members with too much information.

- Convincing stakeholders that their experiences and opinions are important and relevant for future policies.
- Dissemination of project's results, in particular at local, regional and national levels, could be improved.

Channels:

- Instagram is not the preferred platform for the project's audience, making it challenging to reach relevant stakeholders.
- Barriers due to the lack of digital knowledge in stakeholders.
- Lack of space for local actors and value chain representatives to share their opinions on social media.

Content & Products:

- Language barriers – English content may not be accessible to certain value chain actors.
- Project's deliverables and key documents in general are too long and text intensive. There is need for more visualisation of results.
- Limited production of videos and short clips to illustrate results, key messages or testimonials from various actors.
- Limited partners' capacity into selecting the most relevant scientific information and converting into everyday, understandable language for stakeholders.
- Online/personal communication, including the MOVING podcast, infographics, posters and visual materials are perceived by partners as less useful content.

13.2. Recommendations

The appraisal exercise linked to this deliverable has the purpose of identifying areas of improvement in the Strategy of the project. Based on the experiences in the implementation of communication and dissemination activities so far, it also provides valuable inputs to prepare the final phase of the project.

A series of recommendations have been drawn from the challenges and areas for improvement identified and have been sorted into different categories.

CODE Implementation:

- Simplify information as much as possible to make it understandable and relevant for local/regional stakeholders, while avoiding information overload.
- Develop strategies to effectively engage policymakers at all levels.
- Map out important and relevant annual events and conferences to which MOVING could contribute to maximise its presence and disseminate its results.
- Enhance and incentivise the use of the Communication and Dissemination Monitoring tool by all partners through raising awareness about its importance to the project – e.g. capture all the information and activities performed by the partners and communicate them widely.
- Explore options for ensuring the continuity of the program beyond its current phase.

- Dissemination of project's results at local, regional and national level should be enhanced.

Channels:

- Increase stakeholder engagement on social media, through the newsletter or via the website by encouraging feedback, comments, and questions (e.g. via short quizzes, question boxes, collect queries on articles/blog posts).
- Increase the communication and dissemination at the local level. Exploit existing channels (newsletters, websites, blogs, etc.) of other networks and organisations to disseminate more about MOVING and its results.
- A dedicated webpage could be established to compile and promote the “conclusions” resulting from the cross-referencing efforts across all the sites for each work package. This would provide project participants with concise and easily accessible feedback regarding their contributions to the project on a European scale.
- Prioritise dissemination through scientific journals and conferences to effectively reach and engage scientific audiences.
- Enhance complementary efforts through targeted emails, non-scientific events, and strategic use of media and the website can broaden the reach and impact of MOVING's results.

Content & Products:

- Create documents tailored for researchers, stakeholders in mountain areas, and policy-makers at all levels, highlighting the strength of the results and providing practical recommendations.
- Transform text-intensive reports and project results into more visually appealing formats (factsheets, briefs, maps, infographics, etc.).
- Help creating messages and communication material understandable for the general public.
- Encourage involvement of partners for translating content into their own language to facilitate the engagement of local actors.
- Consider providing more country-specific information in national languages to make the project's materials and communications more appealing and accessible to stakeholders in different regions.

Annex 1. MOVING Exploitation Strategy

1.1 Characterisation Table

The Characterisation table is designed to start the collection of information that will be then reviewed and further integrated during the project life. Partners in charge of the Key Exploitable Result (KER) should fill in the content and discuss it with the ones involved in the finalisation of the KER including the partners that will oversee the testing phase.

KER: Conceptual Analytical Framework	
Problem	Lack of an overall analytical framework to analyse and evaluate mountain value chains' interactions with endogenous and exogenous elements, including with the socio-ecological systems.
Alternative solution	Other Conceptual Frameworks exist, though they do not specifically address mountain value chains. A few examples are listed below: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Filière (1960s), the flow of physical inputs and services in the production of a final product (filière of production, i.e., from input to output, or filière of product i.e. from output to input) (Lauret, 1983; Malassis, 1973); ● Commodity Chain (1970s), similar, derived by dependence theories (Wallerstein, 1974); ● Supply Chain (1980s), similar, more in a logistic management sense (Hugos, 2003); ● Global Commodity Chain (1990s), describing the shift in the organization of global production toward external networks (the so-called "outsourcing wave") (Gereffi & Korzeniewicz, 1994); ● Global Value Chains (GVC 2000s), similar to the previous replacing commodity (that basically means raw undifferentiated material) with value intended as "value added" (Sturgeon, 2008); ● Netchains (2001), Integrating supply chain and network analyses (Lazzarini et al., 2001). ● Socio-Ecological Systems (McGinnis and Ostrom (2014).
Unique Selling Point USP - Unique Value Proposition UVP	MOVING Conceptual Analytical Framework provides a comprehensive approach to understanding, showcasing, and evaluating existing connections, forces and interactions with an impact on/originated from mountain value chains. It is the only conceptual framework focused on mountain value chains and their interactions with underpinning socio-ecological systems.
Description	The MOVING Conceptual Analytical Framework helps to disentangle and explain, with narrative and plain language, key factors, elements and dynamics of mountain value chains.
"Market" – Target market	This KER is intended for scientific audiences (i.e. research institutes, universities).
"Market" – Early Adopters	Scientific partners within the MOVING project.

"Market" - Competitors	Other researchers working on rural and mountain development issues, including EU projects (e.g. Horizon Europe MountResilience, COST Action MARGISTAR). Existing thematic organisations and networks (e.g. Euromontana, NEMOR, ICI-MOD)
Go to Market – Use model	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open access scientific publication to make this KER accessible to a wider audience. • Use of this KER into scientific publications • Use of this KER for facilitating educational curricula
Go to Market - Timing	End of 2024/2025, once the final version of this KER will be available.
Go to Market – IPR Background	D2.4 Conceptual analytical framework (final version) [UNIFI]. No specific restrictions are foreseen for using this background.
Go to Market – IPR Fore-ground	Refinement of the Conceptual Framework, including application to case studies, further improvement etc. No restrictions are set.

KER: 23 Mountain Areas Vulnerabilities and Opportunities through Value Chains

Problem	Mountain value chains' actors lack practical tools to foster mountain resilience and their capacity to adapt to climate change and other threats.
Alternative solution	<p>Solutions and studies to enhance resilience somehow exist at the local and regional scales, concerning some relevant sectors for mountains (e.g. tourism, agriculture). However, such solutions are not available in all regions, they are often fragmented, and might not cover multiple sectors.</p> <p>At the European level, alternative solutions are the Adapt@Altitude platform, Euromontana's collection of successful practices, Interreg tools (e.g. Alpine Space, POCTEFA, Europe).</p> <p>At the global level, alternative solutions are the Mountain Partnership's best practices, MRI Research and Tools (incl. GeoMountains project).</p>
Unique Selling Point USP - Unique Value Proposition UVP	MOVING developed different practical tools (e.g. maps, matrixes, guidelines, inspiring stories, good practices lists, practice abstracts) to build the capacities of local actors. The MOVING approach has been tested and validated across 23 mountain regions in Europe and it considers a variety of factors (social, environmental and economic). This provides our solution not only an integrated approach, but also the widest set of practical tools – thus far – with the highest geographical coverage of Europe's mountains.
Description	MOVING provides a number of tools for value chains' actors across Europe's mountain regions. Tools are intended to simplify and guide the improvement, upgrading and decision-making of mountain value chains to face with existing threats (e.g. climate change, demography).

<p>"Market" – Target market</p>	<p>Mountain value chains' actors, in particular businesses and practitioners (from different sectors: tourism, agriculture, forestry)</p> <p>Regional Decision Makers</p> <p>Regional and local authorities</p> <p>Wannabe-entrepreneurs</p>
<p>"Market" – Early Adopters</p>	<p>Mountain value chains' actors in the MOVING Reference Regions, in particular: MOVING MAPs in 23 regions, CNVP members, AREPO members.</p>
<p>"Market" - Competitors</p>	<p>Different local and regional solutions might exist in different mountain areas. A few instances are local and regional research labs (e.g. Labex ITTEM, CEMONT), consultancies (e.g. ETIFOR), Local Action Groups in selected regions, regional authorities.</p>
<p>Go to Market – Use model</p>	<p>Training</p> <p>Capacity-building sessions</p> <p>Knowledge transfer events</p> <p>Sharing information on platforms</p>
<p>Go to Market - Timing</p>	<p>2024</p>
<p>Go to Market – IPR Background</p>	<p>The main components of this KER are 'D3.1 Land Use Systems and Land Cover Map in 23 Reference Regions' [UEvora] and 'D3.2 Land use systems and vulnerability matrixes and vulnerability maps for the 23 reference regions' [UCO].</p> <p>Additional components:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● D4.3 Participatory analysis of value chains [CZU] ● D4.5 Report on Vulnerability and Resilience Performance of 23 Reference Region Value Chains [HUTTON] ● D3.3 Tools for science-society-policy interfaces (Story Maps) [CNR] ● D1.8 Practice Abstracts (1st batch) [UCO] ● D1.9 Practice Abstracts (2nd batch) [UCO] ● D4.1 Inventory of Mountain value chains [UNIPi] ● D4.7 31 Practice Abstracts [CZU] ● D5.1 Comparative cross-case report on Mountain value chains [UCO] ● D4.4 Digital stories from each reference region [CZU] <p>All components are accessible here: https://www.moving-h2020.eu/. No specific restrictions are foreseen for using this background, except for D3.3, for which the use of the D4Science Infrastructure is permitted in compliance with the following conditions (as set in the Consortium Agreement): "The use of all D4Science Infrastructure services is permitted, without prejudice to the provisions of the Policies and Terms of Use set forth in the following references: - https://www.iubenda.com/privacypolicy/441050; - https://services.d4science.org/cookiepolicy ; https://services.d4science.org/terms-of-use.</p>

Go to Market – IPR Foreground	Further refinement of the tools and adaptation of regional scale.
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KER: Policy Tools	
Problem	More adapted policy frameworks are needed to address the needs of actors along mountain value chains. Policymakers need support to design measures that target the unique needs of these actors.
Alternative solution	Existing policy framework and tools to support mountain value chains and mountain territorial development include national/regional tools (e.g. Avenir Montagne- France, SNAI-Italy, Catalan mountain law, Romanian mountain law), and EU policy frameworks (CAP, Cohesion Policy, Art 174/5 TFEU) and EU-level policy recommendations from relevant networks/organisations (e.g. Euromontana, EU Mountain Convention, Rural Networks, EU CAP Network on Mountains).
Unique Selling Point USP - Unique Value Proposition UVP	MOVING provides a set of policy tools that can be used to improve European, national and regional policy frameworks to support mountain value chains. These are actionable, focused and based on real stakeholder needs. MOVING Policy Tools have been co-developed and validated by more than 900 actors in 23 EU mountain regions. They have been derived in close connection with existing networks (e.g. Euromontana and AREPO) and they provide the ground for an enabling policy framework to address common challenges and shared solutions.
Description	MOVING provides an integrated set of policy tools to guide policy at local, regional, national and European levels. Making use of MOVING findings, is a quick way to improve the wellbeing and resilience of mountain regions in Europe.
"Market" – Target market	Policy and decision-makers at local, regional, national and European levels (e.g. EU Commission (DG Agri); European Parliament; European Committee of the Regions and European Economic and Social Committee; EU agri-food stakeholders participating in Civil Dialogue Groups; Regional authorities).
"Market" – Early Adopters	European and national-level policymakers.
"Market" - Competitors	Existing advocacy and lobbying networks who might have a different position than the one represented by MOVING (e.g. conventional and large farming organisations, COPA COGECA).
Go to Market – Use model	Policy tools will feed into ongoing policy discussion at multiple governing levels, providing evidence from mountain actors and ranges.
Go to Market - Timing	Mid-End of 2024

<p>Go to Market – IPR Background</p>	<p>Core components:</p> <p>D2.5 Final set of Policy briefs [UNIFI]</p> <p>D7.1 Policy Roadmap including the results of the Policy Audit and recommendations for a new generation of public policies and strategies for Europe’s mountain areas [HCC]</p> <p>D7.2 Policy Design Toolkit [HCC]</p> <p>D6.3 Synthesis report, including a Repertoire of Strategic Options [ORIGIN]</p> <p>Additional components:</p> <p>D2.2 Initial set of policy briefs [UNIFI]</p> <p>D5.2 Policy Briefs [UCO]</p> <p>All components are accessible here: https://www.moving-h2020.eu/. No specific restrictions are foreseen for using this background.</p>
<p>Go to Market – IPR Foreground</p>	<p>Contribution and integration of key recommendations into EU post-2027 policy discussion, with an emphasis on Cohesion Policy, CAP, and Territorial Agenda.</p>

1.2 Use Options

KER's Exploitation route (how the KER will be further exploited): MOVING Conceptual Analytical Framework			
Selected route		Implementing actor	Yes
DI R E C T U S E	Commercialisation: <i>deployment of a novel product/service (offered to the target markets)</i>	One partner	
		A group of partners	
	Contract research (<i>new contracts signed by the research group with external clients</i>)	A partner	
		A group of partners	
	A new research project (<i>application to public funded research programmes</i>)	A partner	X
		A group of partners	X
Implementation of a new university – course (<i>Note that a training course is a service</i>)	A partner		
	A group of partners		
	A new partnership		
IN DI R E C T U S E	Assignment of the IPR	A partner	
		A group of partners	
	Licensing of the IPR	A partner	
		A group of partners	
	Development of a new legislation/standard	A partner	
		A group of partners	
	Spin- off	A partner	
		A group of partners	
By assignment			
By licensing			
Other (<i>please describe</i>)			

If more than one option is selected, this should be duly justified e.g., more paths are considered at the same time or final decision not taken yet, etc: A new research project is one of the pre-identified exploitation pathways for the MOVING's project. Individual partners have defined their interests and efforts to identify follow-up research projects, with a particular focus on available funds at the regional and national levels. According to funding opportunities, a group of partners might apply jointly for a project's follow-up.

KER's Exploitation route (how the KER will be further exploited): 23 Mountain Areas Vulnerabilities and Opportunities through Value Chains			
Selected route		Implementing actor	Yes
DI R E C T U S E	Commercialisation: <i>deployment of a novel product/service (offered to the target markets)</i>	One partner	
		A group of partners	
	Contract research (<i>new contracts signed by the research group with external clients</i>)	A partner	
		A group of partners	
	A new research project (<i>application to public funded research programmes</i>)	A partner	
		A group of partners	
Implementation of a new university – course (<i>Note that a training course is a service</i>)	A partner		
	A group of partners		
	A new partnership		
Assignment of the IPR		A partner	

INDIRECT USE		A group of partners	
	Licensing of the IPR	A partner	
		A group of partners	
	Development of a new legislation/standard	A partner	
		A group of partners	
	Spin- off	A partner	X
		A group of partners	
		By assignment	
	By licensing		
	Other (<i>please describe</i>)		

KER's Exploitation route (how the KER will be further exploited): MOVING Policy Tools			
	Selected route	Implementing actor	Yes
DIRECT USE	Commercialisation: <i>deployment of a novel product/service (offered to the target markets)</i>	One partner	
		A group of partners	
	Contract research (<i>new contracts signed by the research group with external clients</i>)	A partner	
		A group of partners	
	A new research project (<i>application to public funded research programmes</i>)	A partner	
		A group of partners	
	Implementation of a new university – course (<i>Note that a training course is a service</i>)	A partner	
		A group of partners	
A new partnership			
INDIRECT USE	Assignment of the IPR	A partner	
		A group of partners	
	Licensing of the IPR	A partner	
		A group of partners	
	Development of a new legislation/standard	A partner	
		A group of partners	X
	Spin- off	A partner	
		A group of partners	
By assignment			
	By licensing		
	Other (<i>please describe</i>)		

1.3 Exploitation roadmap

KER 1: MOVING Conceptual Analytical Framework

The Exploitation Roadmap is a tool designed to help the consortium to identify and plan activities to be performed after the end of the project. The highest risk a consortium faces is not being able to implement the exploitation and dissemination plan and increase the TRL level or go to market, due to lack of resources. The exploitation roadmap is designed to address this risk, mitigate it and pave the way toward use and a stronger impact.

Exploitation roadmap	
Actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific publication on the finalised version of the CAF • Gathering of relevant resources • Follow-up meeting • Uptake of results by research and University partners
Roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research partners: making use of the KER • Practice partners: promoting the results, testing the KER within regional context/value chains
Milestones	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific publication submitted • Meeting minutes
Financials Costs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publication costs • No meeting costs (remote)
Revenues	N/A
Other sources of coverage	Partners resources for covering staff costs and equipment costs (e.g. Internet connection, other research contracts).
Impact in 3-year time	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deepen the understanding of mountain value chains' interactions and dynamics • Contribute to identify key points for leveraging mountain value chains' enhancement

KER 2: 23 Mountain Areas Vulnerabilities and Opportunities through Value Chains

The Exploitation Roadmap is a tool designed to help the consortium identify and plan activities to be performed after the end of the project. The highest risk a consortium faces is not being able to implement the exploitation and dissemination plan and increase the TRL level or go to market, due to lack of resources. The exploitation roadmap is designed to address this risk, mitigate it and pave the way toward use and a stronger impact.

Exploitation roadmap	
Actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Agreement on key tools ● Action plan for bundling the tools together and tailoring to needs ● Definition of governance structure
Roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Lead partner for coordination ● Technical partners ● Support from scientific partners ● Practice partners for reaching out to users in respective regions and promoting the tools
Milestones	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● General meeting organised ● Roles distributed ● Gathering of tools finalised ● Business plan clearly defined and agreed
Financials Costs	Partners resources for covering staff costs and equipment costs (e.g. Internet connection). Technical infrastructure might be needed.
Revenues	Grants used to this scope Cohesion Policy support (ESF+, ERDF) CAP support (e.g. LEADER, other objectives) Paid revenues from the commercialisation of tools/training on tools
Other sources of coverage	N/A
Impact in 3-year time	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Increase the capacity of mountain value chains' actors to address current and future threats. ● Identify, improve and rollout upgrading strategies for mountain value chains ● Develop a network of regional mountain stakeholders improved skills

KER 3: MOVING Policy Tools

The Exploitation Roadmap is a tool designed to help the consortium to identify and plan activities to be performed after the end of the project. The highest risk a consortium faces is not being able to implement the exploitation and dissemination plan and increase the TRL level or go to market, due to lack of resources. The exploitation roadmap is designed to address this risk, mitigate it and pave the way toward use and a stronger impact.

Exploitation roadmap	
Actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Agreement on key tools ● Action plan for bundling the tools together and tailoring to needs ● Definition of governance structure ● Identification of key policy interlocutors ● Definition of advocacy strategy
Roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● European-level partners for the European legislative framework ● Regional and national level partners for regional/national legislative policy framework
Milestones	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Advocacy strategy ● Draft of the post-2027 EU legislation ● Post-2027 CAP Strategic Plans ● Post-2027 Cohesion Policies ● National strategy/policies (as relevant)
Financials Costs	Partners resources for covering staff costs and equipment costs (e.g. Internet connection). Travelling costs.
Revenues	N/A
Other sources of coverage	Existing grants (focusing on policy development/advocacy)
Impact in 3-year time	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ensure that MOVING's results are reflected in a number of key European, national and regional policies and strategies ● Raise capacity-building initiatives, programmes and projects to enhance mountain resilience and sustainability

1.4 Risk Assessment and Priority Map

KER 1: MOVING Conceptual Analytical Framework

Description of Risks	Risk criticality*	Risk probability*	Risk Grade	Potential intervention	Estimated Feasibility/Success of Intervention*
Partnership Risk Factors					
Disagreement on ownership rules	4	3	12	Grant Agreement clearly defines the ownership of this result.	9
Disagreement on further investments: some partners may leave.	7	5	35	Partners are likely to keep with their promises and plan to exploit this KER as already done during the project implementation period. Mountains are the focus of an increasing number of research and practice-oriented projects for which this KER is needed.	8
CAF having gaps and inconsistencies.	4	7	28	Peer-review of the CAP by MOVING and other external experts. Common agreement.	
Market Risk Factors					
Exploitation disagreement: partners with divergent interests.	4	4	16	Diversified use of this KER is possible and would contribute to a further evolution of the Analytical Framework.	5
Nobody buys the product. Nobody needs it.	4	3	12	The product will be mainly used for non-commercial exploitation, i.e. scientific.	2
Financial/Management Risk Factors					
Lack of endorsement from top management	5	1	5	MOVING partners are part of the top management of their respective organisation	8

Weak exploitation: Inadequate business plan	7	6	42	The current exploitation plan is a first step towards the development of a more concrete business plan.	6
No resources (human and/or financial) secured to make the next step toward exploitation	8	5	40	Search for additional fundings to pursue research activities related to this KER and the MOVING project.	4

*(1 low probability- 10 high probability)

KER 2: 23 Mountain Areas Vulnerabilities and Opportunities through Value Chains

Description of Risks	Risk criticality*	Risk Probability*	Risk Grade	Potential intervention	Estimated Feasibility/Success of Intervention*
Partnership Risk Factors					
Disagreement on further investments: some partners may leave.	4	5	20	Partnership agreement before the project's end. Most results within this KER are open access. Leaving or disagreement with any of the partners would not considerably affect the exploitation route.	9
Disagreement on ownership rules	6	3	18	Partnership agreement before the project's end. The large majority of results within this KER are open-access. Leaving or disagreement from any of the partners would not considerably affect the exploitation route.	8
Partners break out and create competitive products	7	3	21	Partnership agreement before the project's end; definition of different markets	
Technological Risk Factors					

Lack of technological structure to collect all tools together	9	5	45	Contracting technical staff; Deploying existing technical infrastructure and expertise.	7
Market Risk Factors					
Nobody buys the product. Product not tailored to market needs (i.e. language, regional context)	8	6	48	Market segmentation strategies	2
Existence of better competitors	10	7	70	Develop a marketing strategy to convey the added value of these tools (i.e. integration rather than deepness); Continuous improvement of the tools	5
Financial/Management Risk Factors					
Lack of endorsement from top management	9	5	45	Spin-off companies; follow-up exploitation mainly by business and private partners	8
Weak exploitation: Inadequate business plan	6	4	24	Support for business plan development	6
No resources (human and/or financial) secured to make the next step toward exploitation	8	4	32	Search for financial resources to provide adequate resource flowing in the exploitation plan implementation	4

*(1 low probability- 10 high probability)

KER 3: MOVING Policy Tools

Description of Risks	Risk criticality*	Risk probability*	Risk Grade	Potential intervention	Estimated Feasibility/Success of Intervention*
Partnership Risk Factors					
Disagreement on ownership rules	6	3	18	Clarification of ownership rules before project's end	9
Delays in products' delivery	7	7	49	Careful coordination from the project's top management	8
Market Risk Factors					
Market Demand. Products are not developed in proper timing	9	3	27	Alignment with policy cycle	5
Financial/Management Risk Factors					
No resources (human and/or financial) secured to make the next step toward exploitation	8	5	40	Reliance over advocacy groups within MOVING network and other EU stakeholder networks; Search for resources for KER exploitation; Strategy adaptation to existing resources	8

*(1 low probability- 10 high probability)